

Research Article

The Effect of Environment on Combining Ability and Heterosis in Hybrid Rice

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ABSTRACT

Study was undertaken to estimate the combining ability and heterosis for yield and yield contributing characters over environments. Environment, Crosses, GCA and SCA, and their various interactions with environment were significant suggesting that the hybrids did not have the same relative performances among environments. An evaluation of combining ability across the environment indicated that both general and specific combining ability effects are important but predominance of non-additive genetic variance indicated the presence of heterozygosity in the population. As such this type of genetic variance is non-fixable hence; heterosis breeding is effective for crop improvement. Line IR-79156A, IR-68897 and tester R-51 during both the seasons and testers R-47, R-48, R-49, R-52, IR-64 and IR-10198 during *kharif* and line R-42, IR-66, R-43, R-46, R-56 and IR-13419 during *rabi* were the promising general combiners for grain yield per plant and other traits. These parents used as testers and lines in the cross combinations would be able to realize good hybrids. Considering high physical grain quality parameters as well as *per se* performance, *sca* effects (High x high or high x low *gca* effects of each cross) and standard heterosis, hybrids viz., IR-80555A x R-51 and IR-79156A x R-44 during *kharif* and IR-79156A x R-43, IR-68897A x R-51 and IR-68897A x R-52 during *rabi* have been identified as promising rice hybrids.

In breeding programs, information on combining ability and heterosis of parents and crosses over the environments is very important. Combining ability analysis is one of the powerful tools available to estimate the combining ability effects and aids in selecting the desirable parents and crosses for the exploitation of heterosis (Sarker et al. (2002); Rashid et al. (2007) and Selvaraj et al. (2011)). Heterosis is an important way of increasing yield and improving quality in crops. Since 1914, when the term 'heterosis' was coined and first proposed by G. H. Shull, genetic research on heterosis has been an important issue. Since heterosis over environments is variable (Virmani et al. (1982) and Young & Virmani, (1990) and environment-dependent Knight, (1973). The genetic basis of heterosis *per se* is very complicated. The expression of heterosis varied with the crosses and also with characters (Tiwari, *et al.* (2011)). To know the potentiality of hybrids, the magnitude and direction of heterosis is important (Singh et al. (1955)). The magnitude of heterosis depends on the degree of genetic distinctiveness of the parental lines used while; both positive and negative heterosis is useful for crop improvement, depending on objectives of the breeding. An estimate of combining ability and heterosis is known to be greatly influenced by the environment. The results of combining ability analysis and heterosis based on single environment do not take into account genotype by environment interaction and so results obtained might be highly biased. Therefore, the results based on several environments would be more useful which take into account the stability of gene action. In this paper, an attempt has been made to assess the combining ability and to determine the nature and magnitude of gene action for yield and yield-related traits to explore the best combination of male sterile and restorer lines for the exploitation of maximum heterosis or hybrid vigor over environments.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The material for the present study comprised 68 F₁S of rice generated by crossing four CMS lines (WA source) viz., DRR-14A, IR-80555A, IR-79156A and IR-68897A and seventeen elite diverse restorer lines (R-42(IR-55838), R-43(IR-72), R-44 (UPRI-92133), R-46(IR-63883-41-3-2-2R), R-47(NDR 3026-1R), R-48(IR-33569-26-2-2R), R-49(IR-56381-139-2-2R), R-51(IR-60819-44-2-1R), R-52(IR-60919-150-3-3-3-2R), R-54(IR-62037-12-1-2-2R), R-56(IR-63877-43-2-1-3-1R), IR-64, IR-66, IR-13419, IR-10198, DRR-714 (DRR-714-1-2-R) and JGL 11118) through Line x Tester design during *rabi*, 2007-2008 at Regional Agricultural Research Station, Jagtial, Karimnagar Dist,

Andhra Pradesh, India. The resultant 68 hybrids and 21 parents were evaluated in randomized block design with 4m length of two rows each with 20 x 15cm spacing during *kharif* 2008 and 15 x 15cm spacing during *rabi* 2008-09 in two replications at two major rice growing locations viz., Regional Agricultural Research Station, Jagtial (Latitude 18° 48' N and Longitude 78° 24' E) for Northern Telangana Agro-climatic Zone and Agricultural Research Station, Kampasagar (Latitude 16° 52' 0 N and Longitude 79° 34' 60 E) for Southern Telangana Agro-climatic Zone of Andhra Pradesh. Observations were recorded on five plants at random in each replication. Data recorded on yield and yield contributing characters.

Statistical analysis:

Combined analyses of variance were done for the data pooled of two locations for Kharif and rabi separately according to Gomez and Gomez (1984) after carrying out homogeneity test. The genetic analysis was performed using line x tester analysis according to Kempthorne (1957). Additionally, the procedures described by Singh and Chudhary (1977) were used to estimate General Combining Ability (GCA) effects for each female and male parents and Specific Combining Ability (SCA) effects for hybrid combinations. The standard heterosis was calculated against the DRRH 2 (Hybrid) and JGL-1798 (Variety). Comparing these values with critical difference values tested the statistical significance of heterosis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Analysis of Variance: The combined analysis of variance for Kharif and rabi seasons (Table 1a &b) indicated that mean squares due to environment, environment and treatment were significant for all the traits except spikelet fertility, 1000 grain weight, flag leaf width and filled grains per panicle in both seasons. The mean squares due to environment and environment for line and tester were significant across the seasons for days to 50% flowering, plant height, panicle length, panicle weight, flag leaf width spikelet fertility, filled grains per panicle, grain yield per plant and productivity per day. The environments vs. (Line vs. tester) were significant for most of the traits over seasons. Environment x crosses was significant for most of the characters. Environment x line x tester effect was significant for all the traits studied during both seasons. Environment, Crosses, GCA and SCA, and their various interactions with environment were significant suggesting that the hybrids did not have the same relative performances among environments.

Table 1a: Variance components of general and specific combining ability and their interactions for kharif and rabi seasons for yield and yield components in hybrid rice

Source	Df	Days to 50% flowering		Plant height (cm)		Panicle length (cm)		Panicle weight (g)		Productive tillers per plant		Flag leaf length (cm)	
		Kharif	Rabi	Kharif	Rabi	Kharif	Rabi	Kharif	Rabi	Kharif	Rabi	Kharif	Rabi
Replicates	1	29.80**	7.31	9	6.06	0.06	24.87**	0.24*	0.77**	0.71	0.43	1.96	0.03
Environments	1	1021.4**	113.49**	939.09**	15620.7**	35.68**	334.28**	16.14**	0.30**	41.60**	48.54**	26.98**	315.07**
Rep * Env.	1	41.13**	0.07	40.72**	5.14**	14.76**	11.98*	0.02	0.02	6.23*	0.36	3.8	0.05
Env * Treat	88	23.02**	37.07**	41.56**	86.18**	4.39**	5.73	0.55**	0.19**	3.23**	2.98**	9.90**	6.61**
Env * Parents	20	20.37**	25.78**	90.87**	114.03**	6.33**	4	0.33**	0.09**	2.47**	2.81**	5.76**	1.87**
Env * Parents (L)	3	29.56**	6.92	174.54**	201.12**	1.18	11.20*	0.64**	0.03	2.89	5.19**	1.32	1.69*
Env * Parents (T)	16	15.57**	30.06**	39.19**	100.54**	7.55**	2.73	0.29**	0.10**	2.54**	2.37**	6.01**	2.02**
Env * PAR (L vs T)	1	69.71**	13.92	666.73**	68.61**	2.39	2.73	0.01	0.11	0.06	2.71	14.97*	0.05
Env * Parent vs Cross	1	62.39**	163.93**	1.46	1396.50**	4.39	5.21	0.41**	0.33**	19.99**	0.68	30.89**	2.16*
Env * Crosses	67	23.22**	38.54**	27.44**	58.30**	3.80**	6.25**	0.61**	0.22**	3.20**	3.07**	10.83**	8.09**
Env * Line effect	3	57.52	8.33	6.62	31.19	13.13*	10.49	0.68	0.48	13.41**	6.4	38.88*	3.1
Env * Tester effect	16	19.92	23.07	45.59*	66.87	3.35	8.58	0.67	0.14	2.8	3.47	7.32	10.71
Env * L * T effect	48	22.17**	45.59**	22.69**	57.14**	3.38**	5.22**	0.59**	0.23**	2.70**	2.73**	10.25**	7.52**
Error	176	2.64	7.8	2.93	2.86	1.83	3.07	0.04	0.04	1.1	1.02	2.84	0.48
Total	355	39.51	30.58	61.15	106.22	4.59	7.38	0.41	0.24	3.27	3.11	10.39	7.95
σ^2_{gca}		7.109	3.4624	25.443	12.2641	1.11	1.0012	0.034	0.0397	0.674	1.2862	5.196	2.236
σ^2_{sca}		18.6	9.0998	28	21.7551	0.713	2.0168	0.226	0.1661	1.026	4.9433	1.89	10.3218
$\sigma^2_{gca}/\sigma^2_{Sca}$		0.382	0.3805	0.909	0.5637	1.557	0.4965	0.15	0.2392	0.657	0.2602	2.749	0.2166

Table 1b: Variance components of general and specific combining ability and their interactions for kharif and rabi seasons for yield and yield components in hybrid rice

Source	Df	Flag leaf width (cm)		Spikelet fertility (%)		Filled grains per panicle		Grain yield per plant (g)		1000 grain weight (g)		Productivity per day(Kg/ha)	
		Kharif	Rabi	Kharif	Rabi	Kharif	Rabi	Kharif	Rabi	Kharif	Rabi	Kharif	Rabi
Replicates	1	0.07**	0.0031	0.01	5.3766	87.8	296.12**	2.58	0.0909	0.19	0.8032	6.77	3787.40**
Environments	1	0.07**	97.08**	0.01	5.38	87.8	296.12**	2.58	0.09	0.19	0.8032	6.77	3787.40**
Rep * Env.	1	0.03*	3805.2**	1444.88**	752.53**	46929.32**	4525.34**	1012.92**	153.32**	60.20**	00.002	7107.66**	1000.78**
Env * Treat	88	0.01	0.31	0.32	0.41	114.85	4.42	10.35*	41.60**	0.001	0.0047	29.4	1969.44**
Env * Parents	20	0.001	29.94**	80.49**	101.95**	1313.59**	783.96**	19.02**	14.20**	9.22**	0.0002	97.70**	149.84**
Env * Parents (L)	3	0.001	33.00**	35.20**	32.55**	955.35**	395.90**	12.78**	13.02**	10.82**	0.0003	56.98**	126.54**
Env * Parents (T)	16	0.01	40.24**	53.81**	12.4	1550.53**	73.46	2.41	6.37	4.44**	0.0003	15.96	125.24*
Env * PAR (L vs T)	1	0.001	31.73**	33.53**	23.72**	902.84**	476.55**	15.31**	14.78**	11.71**	0.0003	68.16**	133.85**
Env * Parent vs Cross	1	0.002	31.61*	6.21	234.32**	9.99	72.88	3.35	4.83	15.62**	0.0001	1.22	13.52
Env * Crosses	67	0.003	588.67**	13.95*	227.12**	12678.56**	629.67**	1.75	0.07	8.87**	0.0001	2.22	105.1
Env * Line effect	3	0.001	20.68**	95.00**	120.80**	1250.90**	902.11**	21.14**	14.76**	8.75**	0.0002	111.28**	157.46**
Env * Tester effect	16	0.001	20.79	51.7	308.01*	6489.44**	137.2	10.29	9.33	23.39*	0.0002	172.79	254.05
Env * L * T effect	48	0.001	20.27	185.02**	160.83	677.67	858.99	18.51	13.4	12.57*	0.0003	102.72	164.69
Error	176	0.001	20.81**	67.69**	95.75**	1114.56**	964.29**	22.69**	15.55**	6.56**	0.0002	110.28**	149.02**
Total	355	0.01	6.89	2.77	9.87	105.7	41.83	1.81	3.17	0.98	1.6824	14.97	32.76
σ^2_{gca}		0.008	0.0623	6.353	18.3794	32.776	13.144	0.154	0.336	0.816	0.468	8.112	6.443
σ^2_{sca}		0.013	1.6147	30.452	54.9211	323.905	190.3	2.135	3.596	2.714	7.1748	59.743	72.453
$\sigma^2_{gca}/\sigma^2_{Sca}$		0.615	0.0386	0.209	0.3347	0.1012	0.0691	0.0721	0.0934	0.301	0.0652	0.136	0.0899

General combining ability (GCA):

The estimates of *gca* effects showed that parents with high *gca* effects differed for various yield and yield components traits over both seasons due to the presence of genotype and environment interactions. The negative estimates of *gca* and *sca* for days to 50 per cent flowering and plant height and positive for remaining characters are considered to be favourable. Promising general combiners for yield and other traits in hybrid rice are illustrated in table 2. Among the lines, IR-79156A identified as best combiner for panicle length, panicle weight, flag leaf length, spikelet fertility and grain yield per plant and IR-68897A for days to 50 per cent flowering, panicle weight, spikelet fertility, 1000 grain weight, productivity per day and grain yield per plant over the both seasons. However, IR-80555A and DRR-14A had favourable genotypes for plant height and productive tillers per plant during both *kharif* and *rabi* season; and IR-80555A for grain yield per plant during *kharif* and 1000 grain weight and productivity per day during *rabi*. Among the testers, R-51 possessed the desirable genes for panicle length, panicle weight, filled grains per panicle and grain yield per plant in both seasons. Among the testers, during *kharif*, R-47 contributed positive alleles for flag leaf width, productive tillers per plant, filled grains per panicle, productivity per day and grain yield per plant; R-48 for flag leaf length, flag leaf width, 1000 grain weight, productivity per day and grain yield per plant; R-49 for days to 50 per cent

flowering, plant height, flag leaf length, filled grain per panicle, productivity per day and grain yield per plant; R-52 for panicle weight, plant height, filled grain per panicle, productivity per day and grain yield per plant; R-56 for panicle weight, flag leaf width, flag leaf length, productive tillers per plant and productivity per day; IR-64 for panicle length, panicle weight, spikelet fertility, 1000 grain weight, filled grains per panicle and grain yield per plant; IR-10198 for days to 50 per cent flowering, plant height, flag leaf width, productive tillers per plant, spikelet fertility and 1000 grain weight. During *rabi*, R-42 had contributed positive alleles for plant height, panicle weight, flag leaf width, 1000 grain weight and grain yield per plant, similarly, R-43 for panicle weight, spikelet fertility and grain yield per plant; R-46 for plant height, flag leaf length, productive tillers per plant and spikelet fertility; IR-66 for days to 50 per cent flowering, panicle weight, productive tillers per plant, spikelet fertility, 1000 grain weight and grain yield per plant and IR-13419 for spikelet fertility, filled grains per panicle and grain yield per plant. All these parents contributed maximum positive alleles for the increase in grain yield per plant during *rabi*.

From the above perusal it may be concluded that lines namely IR-79156A, IR-68897A and tester R-51 performed well under both seasons. Considering the yield and yield contributing traits, restorer lines R-47, R-48, R-49, R-52, R-56, IR-64 and IR-10198 registered promising general combiners for *kharif* and R-42, IR-66, R-43, R-46 and IR-13419 for *rabi* season.

Table 2: Promising general combiners for yield and other traits in hybrid rice during *kharif* and *rabi*

S.No.	Parents	Characters
Both seasons		
1	IR-79156A	Panicle length, panicle weight, flag leaf length, spikelet fertility and grain yield per plant
2	IR-68897A	Days to 50 per cent flowering, panicle weight, spikelet fertility, 1000 grain weight, productivity per day and grain yield per plant
3	R-51	Panicle length, panicle weight, filled grains per panicle and grain yield per plant
Kharif		
1	R-47	Flag leaf width, productive tillers per plant, filled grains per panicle, productivity per day and grain yield per plant
2	R-48	Flag leaf length, flag leaf width, 1000 grain weight, productivity per day and grain yield per plant
3	R-49	Days to 50 per cent flowering, plant height, flag leaf length, filled grain per panicle, productivity per day and grain yield per plant
4	R-52	Panicle weight, plant height, filled grain per panicle, productivity per day and grain yield per plant
5	R-56	Panicle weight, flag leaf width, flag leaf length, productive tillers per plant and productivity per day
6	IR-64	Panicle length, panicle weight, spikelet fertility, 1000 grain weight, filled grains per panicle and grain yield per plant
7	IR-10198	Days to 50 per cent flowering, plant height, flag leaf width, productive tillers per plant, spikelet fertility and 1000 grain weight
Rabi		
1	R-42	Plant height, panicle weight, flag leaf width, 1000 grain weight and grain yield per plant
2	R-43	Panicle weight, spikelet fertility and grain yield per plant
3	R-46	Plant height, flag leaf length, productive tillers per plant, and spikelet fertility
4	IR-66	Days to 50 per cent flowering, panicle weight, productive tillers per plant, spikelet fertility, 1000 grain weight and grain yield per plant
5	IR-13419	spikelet fertility, filled grains per panicle and grain yield per plant

Specific Combining ability:

Top promising crosses with desirable *sca* effects for various traits along with mean performance and *gca* effects of parents involved in the crosses are listed in the table 3. In the present investigation, none of the crosses exhibited high specific combining ability (*sca*) effects for all the characters. Subramanian and Rathinam (1984), Gosh (1993) and Tiwari et al. (2011) also observed that no specific combination was desirable for all the traits in their study. The desirable performances of combinations like high x high were observed in the hybrids; IR-68897A x R-49 (for earliness), IR-79156A x R-56, IR-80555A x R-52 (panicle length), IR-79156A x R-56 (flag leaf length), DRR-14A x R-47, IR-80555A x R-42 (productive tillers per plant), DRR-14A x R-54 (grain yield per plant) during *kharif* and DRR-14A x IR-13419, IR-80555A x IR-64, DRR-14A x R-54 (productive tillers per plant), IR-68897A x IR-13419 (spikelet fertility) and IR-80555A x R-56 (1000 grain weight) during *rabi*. Kalitha and Upadhaya (2000); Shivani et al. (2009); Salgotra et al. (2009), Thiwari et al. (2011) and Saidaiah et al. (2011) also reported high x high combiners which can be fixed in subsequent generations if no repulsion phase linkages are involved.

In general, it is also interesting to note that the crosses showing maximum significant *sca* effects were invariably associated with high *per se* performance for particular traits but this behaviour was not always true for all the characters, thus suggesting that criteria for the selection of crosses on the basis of either mean performance or *sca* effects alone would not prove effective. It is obvious that best cross combinations are not always found between high x high general combiners but may also occur in other types of parental combinations. Parents with highest *gca* effects will not necessarily generate top specific cross combinations as also reported by Singh (1977) and Rao et al. (1980).

The cross combinations during *kharif*, IR-80555A x JGL-11118 (for earliness), DRR-14A x IR-64, IR-68897A x R-44, IR-68897A x R-51 (dwarfism), IR-68897A x JGL-11118 (panicle weight), IR-68897A x R-51, IR-79156A x R-42 (flag leaf length), IR-79156A x JGL-11118, IR-80555A x R-46, IR-79156A x R-51 (flag leaf width), IR-68897A x IR-10198, IR-80555A x IR-66, DRR-14A x R-48 (productive tillers per plant), IR-79156A x R-56, IR-79156A x IR-13419, IR-68897A x R-47 (spikelet fertility), DRR-14A x R-47, IR-80555A x R-49, IR-79156A x R-56, IR-79156A x R-48 (filled grains per panicle), DRR-14A x R-52, IR-79156A x R-44 (grain yield per plant), IR-68897A x R-52, IR-79156A x R-49, IR-79156A x IR-10198 (1000 grain weight), DRR-14A x R-52, IR-79156A x R-44, IR-68897A x DRR-714-2-R, IR-68897A x JGL-11118 (productivity per day) and during *rabi* IR-80555A x IR-66, IR-68897A x R-43 (for earliness), DRR-14A x IR-13419, IR-80555A x IR-10198 (dwarfism), IR-68897A x IR-13419, IR-68897A x

R-54, IR-68897A x IR-64 (panicle length), DRR-14A x R-42, IR-68897A x R-44, DRR-14A x R-48 (panicle weight), IR-68897A x R-48 (flag leaf length), DRR-14A x R-46, (productive tillers per plant), IR-68897A x R-44, IR-80555A x IR-10198, IR-79156A x R-52 (spikelet fertility), DRR-14A x R-47, IR-68897A x R-48 (filled grains per panicle), IR-68897A x R-52, IR-79156A x IR-13419, IR-68897A x R-51 (grain yield per plant), IR-68897A x R-52, IR-79156A x IR-13419, IR-68897A x R-48, IR-68897A x R-51 (1000 grain weight), DRR-14A x R-52, IR-79156A x R-44 (productivity per day) were observed with high x low combinations. Saidaiah et al. (2011) also reported the possibility of interaction between positive alleles from good combiner and negative alleles from poor combiner in high x low cross combination.

Involvement of both the poor combiners also produced superior specific combining cross combinations as evidenced from combinations like DRR-14A x R-42, IR-79156A x R-42, IR-79156A x DRR-714-1-2-R (for earliness), IR-79156A x R-54 (dwarfism), DRR-14A x R-46, DRR-14A x JGL-11118, IR-68897A x R-51 (panicle length), DRR-14A x R-47, DRR-14A x R-54, IR-80555A x IR-10198, IR-68897A x R-56 (panicle weight), DRR-14A x R-44, IR-80555A x R-44 (flag leaf length), IR-68897A x R-43, IR-68897A x R-42 (flag leaf width), DRR-14A x R-43 (spikelet fertility), IR-79156A x IR-13419 (filled grains per panicle), DRR-14A x R-42, IR-68897A x DRR-714-1-2-R (grain yield per plant), IR-79156A x R-44, IR-80555A x R-52 (1000 grain weight), DRR-14A x R-42 (productivity per day) during *kharif* and IR-79156A x R-49, IR-79156A x R-47, IR-79156A x R-54 (for earliness), IR-79156A x R-49, IR-68897A x R-52 (dwarfism), IR-80555A x R-44 (panicle length), IR-80555A x R-47, IR-80555A x R-44 (panicle weight), IR-68897A x R-47, IR-80555A x R-44, IR-68897A x R-51 (flag leaf length), IR-80555A x JGL-11118, IR-68897A x R-46 (flag leaf width), DRR-14A x R-42 (spikelet fertility), DRR-14A x R-46, IR-80555A x R-66, DRR-14A x R-42 (filled grains per panicle), DRR-14A x R-48 (grain yield per plant), IR-68897A x JGL-11118, IR-68897A x DRR-714-1-2-R (productivity per day) during *rabi*. Two poor combiners resulting into crosses with high positive *sca* effects might be due to better nicking ability of the parents. The poor general combiners tended to produce significant *sca* effects in the hybrids, where in the parental combinations provided environment for full expression of genes controlling this trait, though the parent themselves would not express any superiority. Accumulation of favourable genes might be the cause of parents with poor *gca* giving rise to hybrids with higher *sca* effects. Similar results were also reported by Singh et al. (2005), Dalvi and Patel (2009) and Saidaiah et al. (2011); involvement of both the combiners with low *gca* has been attributed to over dominance and epistasis interaction.

Table 3: Top promising crosses with high *sca* effects, *per se* performance and *gca* effects of parents for grain yield and its component traits

Character/ cross	Mean	SCA effects	GCA effects of parents		GCA status	Character/ cross	Mean	SCA effects	GCA effects of parents		GCA status
			Female	Male					Female	Male	
Kharif						Rabi					
Days to 50% flowering						Days to 50% flowering					
DRR-14A x R-42	84.3	-8.779**	-0.346	0.426	LxL	IR-80555A x IR-66	95.0	-9.982**	0.982**	-4.54**	LxH
IR-79156A x R-42	86.5	-6.544**	-0.331	0.426	LxL	IR-79156A x R-49	92.5	-5.912**	2.099**	0.265	LxL
IR-80555A x JGL-11118	84.8	-6.033**	3.346**	-5.511**	LxH	IR-79156A x R-47	92.8	-5.162**	2.099**	-0.235	LxL
IR-79156A x DRR-714-1-2-R	90.3	-5.982	-0.3331	3.614**	LxL	IR-68897A x R-43	94.5	-2.640**	-0.79**	1.890**	HxL
IR-68897A x R-49	85.8	-5.478**	-2.669**	-2.136**	HxH	IR-79156A x R-54	97.3	-2.599**	2.099**	1.702**	LxL
Plant height						Plant height					
IR-79156A x R-54	100.9	-9.967**	8.117**	2.843**	LxL	DRR-14A x IR-13419	59.5	-9.328**	-5.00**	1.105**	HxL
DRR-14A x IR-64	92.8	-9.444**	-1.731**	4.618**	HxL	IR-80555A x IR-10198	62.2	-10.22**	-0.381*	0.080	HxL
IR-68897A x R-44	87.4	-8.981**	-4.032**	0.456	HxL	IR-79156A x R-49	70.1	-7.799**	4.149**	1.024**	LxL
DRR-14A x JGL-11118	89.1	-7.394**	-1.731**	-1.732**	HxH	IR-68897A x R-52	70.6	-5.310**	1.235**	1.924**	LxL
IR-68897A x R-51	91.2	-6.299**	-4.032**	1.549**	HxL	IR-80555A x R-42	64.3	-5.168**	-0.381*	-2.91**	HxH
Panicle length						Panicle length					
DRR-14A x R-46	27.3	2.689**	-0.764**	0.213	LxL	IR-80555A x R-44	22.1	3.205**	-0.238	-1.63**	LxL
IR-79156A x R-56	25.6	2.442**	1.683**	1.388**	HxH	IR-68897A x IR-13419	24.0	2.454**	1.303**	0.649	HxL
IR-80555A x R-52	26.1	2.067**	1.683**	0.788**	HxH	IR-68897A x R-54	21.9	1.939**	1.303**	-0.858*	HxL
DRR-14A x JGL-11118	24.2	1.514**	-0.564**	-0.062	LxL	IR-68897A x IR-64	21.3	1.671**	1.303**	-1.27**	HxL
IR-68897A x R-51	25.2	1.487**	-0.356*	-1.418**	LxL						
Panicle weight						Panicle weight					
IR-68897A x JGL-11118	4.3	0.878**	0.054*	-0.041	HxL	DRR-14A x R-42	3.4	1.004**	-0.17**	0.376**	LxH
DRR-14A x R-47	4.1	0.867**	-0.211**	0.009	LxL	IR-80555A x R-47	2.5	0.587**	-0.17**	-0.049	LxL
DRR-14A x R-54	3.8	0.767**	-0.211**	-0.166**	LxL	IR-80555A x R-44	2.1	0.547**	-0.17**	-0.37**	LxL
IR-80555A x IR-10198	3.9	0.671**	-0.046*	-0.160**	LxL	IR-68897A x R-44	2.5	0.524**	0.182**	-0.37**	HxL
IR-68897A x R-56	4.3	0.628**	0.054*	0.234**	HxH	DRR-14A x R-48	2.9	0.505**	-0.17**	0.395**	LxH
Flag leaf length						Flag leaf length					
IR-68897A x R-51	28.4	8.672**	1.003**	0.237	HxL	IR-68897A x R-47	26.9	4.652**	0.598	-2.57**	LxL
IR-79156A x R-42	32.1	5.665**	2.085**	-0.288	HxL	DRR-14A x R-44	27.1	4.653**	-0.83**	-0.968	LxL
DRR-14A x R-44	29.3	5.644**	-1.644**	-0.488	LxL	IR-68897A x R-48	32.7	4.383**	0.598	3.451**	LxH
IR-79156A x R-56	36.5	5.215**	2.085**	1.362**	HxH	IR-80555A x R-44	26.0	4.309**	-1.61**	-0.968	LxL
IR-80555A x R-44	30.3	5.194**	-1.444**	-0.488	LxL	IR-68897A x R-51	29.0	4.421**	0.598	-0.212	LxL
Flag leaf width						Flag leaf width					
IR-68897A x R-43	1.4	0.264**	-0.132**	-0.036*	LxL	IR-80555A x JGL-11118	1.2	0.147**	0.010	-0.050	LxL

Character/ cross	Mean	SCA effects	GCA effects of parents		GCA status	Character/ cross	Mean	SCA effects	GCA effects of parents		GCA status
			Female	Male					Female	Male	
Kharif						Rabi					
IR-68897A x R-42	1.4	0.226**	-0.132**	-0.023	LxL	IR-68897A x R-46	1.2	0.132**	0.012	0.013	LxL
IR-79156A x JGL-11118	1.5	0.162**	0.069**	-0.036*	HxL						
IR-80555A x R-46	1.4	0.152**	0.010**	-0.092**	HxL						
IR-79156A x R-51	1.5	0.143**	0.069**	0.008	HxL						
Productive tillers per plant						Productive tillers per plant					
IR-68897A x IR-10198	11.5	2.762**	-1.306**	0.516*	LxH	DRR-14A x R-46	4.8	4.216**	1.135**	-0.444*	HxL
IR-80555A x IR-66	12.9	2.645**	0.499**	0.178	HxL	DRR-14A x IR-13419	7.2	3.329**	1.135**	2.536**	HxH
DRR-14A x R-47	13.1	2.650**	0.281*	1.291**	HxH	IR-80555A x IR-64	9.0	3.842**	0.802**	1.356**	HxH
DRR-14A x R-48	12.2	1.975**	0.281*	0.391	HxL	DRR-14A x R-54	7.7	2.954**	1.135**	1.336**	HxH
IR-80555A x R-42	12.1	1.545**	0.499**	0.478*	HxH						
Spikelet fertility						Spikelet fertility					
DRR-14A x R-43	86.7	8.815**	-3.165**	-0.484**	LxL	DRR-14A x R-42	87.5	11.436**	0.030	-1.697*	LxL
IR-79156A x R-56	90.3	8.299**	1.745**	-1.178**	HxL	IR-68897A x R-44	91.4	10.789**	4.287**	-1.314	HxL
IR-80555A x R-49	86.4	7.872**	-1.022**	-1.909**	LxL	IR-80555A x IR-10198	90.3	9.640**	-6.10**	9.106**	LxH
IR-79156A x IR-13419	89.4	7.724**	1.745**	-1.578**	HxL	IR-79156A x R-52	86.7	8.990**	1.783**	-1.779*	HxL
IR-68897A x R-47	88.7	6.820**	2.442**	-2.022**	HxL	IR-68897A x IR-13419	92.8	8.897**	4.287**	1.898*	HxH
Filled grains per panicle						Filled grains per panicle					
DRR-14A x R-47	171.5	39.086**	-4.236**	14.314**	LxH	DRR-14A x R-46	106.7	28.127**	1.315	-2.918	LxL
IR-80555A x R-49	161.8	31.535**	2.128	5.752*	LxH	IR-80555A x R-66	108.2	24.385**	0.876	2.739	LxL
IR-79156A x R-56	154.9	29.200**	4.688**	-1.273	HxL	DRR-14A x R-42	102.4	20.380**	1.315	0.572	LxL
IR-79156A x R-48	137	24.168**	4.688**	-14.16**	HxL	DRR-14A x R-47	111.5	20.244**	1.315	9.790**	LxH
IR-79156A x IR-13419	143.2	22.031**	-2.580*	-5.854*	LxL	IR-68897A x R-48	103.9	17.870**	-0.619	6.516**	LxH
1000-grain weight						1000-grain weight					
IR-68897A x R-52	25.4	2.379**	0.458**	-0.140	HxL	IR-68897A x R-52	25.0	20.745**	1.985**	-5.44**	HxL
IR-79156A x R-49	25.9	1.983**	0.036	1.179**	LxH	IR-79156A x IR-13419	22.0	16.823**	-2.07**	5.604**	LxH
IR-79156A x IR-10198	25.9	1.970**	0.036	1.142**	LxH	IR-68897A x R-48	24.8	12.047**	1.985**	0.735	HxL
IR-79156A x R-44	23.8	1.858**	0.036	-0.846**	LxL	IR-68897A x R-51	24.8	12.001**	1.985**	2.163	HxL
IR-80555A x R-52	24.0	1.665**	-0.252*	-0.140	LxL	IR-80555A x R-56	22.9	11.983**	1.799**	3.055*	HxH
Productivity per day						Productivity per day					
DRR-14A x R 42	59.3	16.27**	-3.21**	0.61	LxL	DRR-14A x R-42	55.8	16.267**	-3.21**	0.608	LxL
DRR-14A x R 52	61.3	14.79**	-3.21**	4.04**	LxH	DRR-14A x R-52	38.2	14.786**	-3.21**	4.039**	LxH
IR-79156A x R 44	60.0	13.57**	1.45*	-0.60	HxL	IR-79156A x R-44	41.0	13.565**	1.454*	-0.604	HxL
IR-68897A x DRR-714-1-R	49.0	10.65**	2.10**	-9.41**	HxL	IR-68897A x JGL-11118		11.835**	2.097	0.358	LxL
IR-68897A x JGL-11118	59.9	11.84**	2.10**	0.36	HxL	IR-68897A x DRR-714-1-2-R	45.0	10.653**	2.097	-9.41**	LxL
Grain yield per plant						Grain yield per plant					

Character/ cross	Mean	SCA effects	GCA effects of parents		GCA status	Character/ cross	Mean	SCA effects	GCA effects of parents		GCA status
			Female	Male					Female	Male	
Kharif						Rabi					
DRR-14A x R-52	28.1	6.42**	-1.59**	2.18**	LxH	IR-68897A x R-48	21.1	4.957**	0.72**	-0.874	HxL
DRR-14A x R-42	25.7	5.86**	-1.59**	0.271	LxL	IR-68897A x R-51	21.6	3.777**	0.72**	0.866	HxL
IR-79156A x R-44	26.1	5.70**	0.565**	-1.29**	HxL	IR-68897A x R-52	19.8	4.880**	0.72**	-2.122**	HxL
IR-68897A x DRR-714-1-2-R	23.0	5.41**	0.281	-3.79**	LxL	IR-79156A x IR-13419	22.6	4.589**	-1.89	1.899**	LxH
DRR-14A x R-54	25.8	5.25**	1.591**	0.983**	HxH	DRR-14A x R-48	17.9	3.54**	-0.95**	-0.874	LxL

It is necessary that the parents involved in the cross combinations should have high *gca* effect to get significant *sca* effect. The reason ascribed is due to positive interaction between nuclear and cytoplasmic genes appearing to be more important than the interaction between nuclear genes alone. High x high or low x low crosses usually results in situations resembling essentially their parents. Whereas high x low crosses produce heterozygous genotypes, which express high effects and consequently are superior to both parents. In the light of results obtained, it appears that the best approach in rice would be to start with high x low type of crosses followed by high x high crosses. The necessity to evaluate the parents for their nicking ability do not cease as grouping of parental lines in to high, average or low helps in selecting the parents and analysis of combining ability of parents in relation to hybrids may provide insight into level of expression of a particular trait in a specific genetic background. In majority of the crosses, high *sca* was either due to high x low or low x low combining parents, which further substantiate the operation of non-additive gene action (additive x dominance and dominance x dominance epistatic interaction). An ideal combination to be explored is one where high magnitude of *sca* is present, in addition to high *gca* in both or at least one of the parents.

Based on *per se* performance and *sca* effects (High x high or high x low *gca* effects of each cross)

crosses viz., DRR-14A x R-42, DRR-14A x R-43, DRR-14A x R-47, DRR-14A x R-54, IR-80555A x R-48, IR-80555A x R-49, IR-80555A x R-51, IR-79156A x R-44, IR-79156A x R-48, IR-68897A x IR-10198, IR-68897A x DRR-714-1-2-R and IR-68897A x JGL-11118 during *khari* were identified as promising (Table 4). However, crosses namely DRR-14A x R-48, IR-80555A x R-47, IR-80555A x R-54, IR-80555A x R-56, IR-80555A x IR-66, IR-79156A x R-43, IR-79156A x IR-13419, IR-79156A x DRR-714-1-2-R, IR-68897A x R-48, IR-68897A x R-51 and IR-68897A x R-52 during *rabi* were identified as promising for grain yield per plant and other yield contributing characters based *per se* performance, *sca* effects (High x high or high x low *gca* effects of each cross) (Table 5).

A comparison of the magnitude of variance components due to GCA and SCA combined the nature of gene action in controlling the expression of the traits. The SCA variances were higher than GCA variances for majority of the characters (except panicle length and flag leaf length during *khari*) over the seasons, revealed that expression of these traits were controlled mostly by the non-additive effects of genes that are stable in over seasons and locations. (Table 1a & b). Predominance of non-additive gene action for grain yield and its components was also reported by Dalvi and Patel (2009, Saidaiah et al. (2011) and Tiwari et al. (2011).

Table 4: Promising specific combiners for yield and yield contributing traits in rice during *kharif*

Hybrid	Mean	SCA effects	GCA effects		Standard heterosis		Characters
			Female	Male	DRRH-2	JGL 1798	
DRR-14A x R-42	25.7	5.86**	-1.59**	0.271	44.2	41.8	Days to 50% flowering, flag leaf length, spikelet fertility, filled grains per panicle and grain yield per plant
DRR-14A x R-43	20.6	2.01**	-1.59**	-0.899**	16.0	14.1	Days to 50% flowering, plant height, flag leaf length, spikelet fertility, filled grains per panicle and grain yield per plant
DRR-14A x R-47	24.2	3.09**	-1.591**	1.539**	35.8	33.6	Panicle weight, productive tillers per plant, spikelet fertility, filled grains per panicle and grain yield per plant
DRR-14A x R-54	25.8	5.25**	-1.591**	0.983**	44.8	42.4	Panicle weight, flag leaf length, flag leaf width, filled grains per panicle and grain yield per plant
IR-80555A x R-48	27.7	3.85**	0.746**	1.95**	55.4	52.9	Panicle weight, flag leaf length, spikelet fertility, filled grains per panicle, 1000 grain weight and grain yield per plant
IR-80555A x R-49	27.6	3.20**	0.746**	2.496**	54.9	52.3	Panicle weight, flag leaf length, spikelet fertility, filled grains per panicle and grain yield per plant
IR-80555A x R-51	25.1	1.81**	0.746**	1.44**	41.2	38.8	Days to 50% flowering, plant height, spikelet fertility, filled grains per panicle and grain yield per plant
IR-79156A x R-44	26.1	5.70**	0.565**	-1.29**	46.6	44.2	Days to 50% flowering, panicle weight, productive tillers per plant, 1000 grain weight and grain yield per plant
IR-79156A x R-48	26.5	2.85**	0.565**	1.95**	48.9	46.4	Plant height, panicle weight, filled grains per panicle and grain yield per plant
IR-68897A x IR-10198	22.5	3.95**	0.281	-2.92**	26.1	24.0	Days to 50% flowering, flag leaf length, productive tillers per plant and grain yield per plant
IR-68897A x DRR-714-1-2-R	23.0	5.41**	0.281	-3.79**	29.3	27.2	flag leaf length, flag leaf width, spikelet fertility and grain yield per plant
IR-68897A x JGL-11118	26.0	5.09**	0.281	-0.48	46.2	43.8	Plant height, panicle length, panicle weight, filled grains per panicle, 1000 grain weight and grain yield per plant

Table 5: Promising specific combiners for yield and yield contributing traits in rice during *rabi*

Hybrid	Mean	SCA effects	GCA effects		Standard heterosis		Characters
			Female	Male	DRRH-2	JGL 1798	
DRR-14A x R-48	17.9	3.54**	-0.95**	-0.874	19.9	26.3	Plant height, panicle weight, spikelet fertility, filled grains per panicle, 1000 grain weight and grain yield per plant
IR-80555A x R-47	20.3	2.155**	0.415	1.471**	36.1	43.3	Panicle weight, productive tillers per plant, filled grains per panicle, grain yield per plant, 1000 grain weight and productivity per day
IR-80555A x R-54	16.8	2.751**	0.415	-2.635**	12.6	18.5	Productive tillers per plant, spikelet fertility, grain yield per plant and 1000 grain weight
IR-80555A x R-56	19.3	2.048**	0.415	0.519	28.9	35.8	Plant height, filled grains per panicle, grain yield per plant and 1000 grain weight
IR-80555A x IR-66	19.7	2.556**	0.415	0.436	31.8	38.8	Days to 50% flowering, spikelet fertility, filled grains per panicle, 1000 grain weight and grain yield per plant
IR-79156A x R-43	20.5	3.183**	-1.89	1.263**	37.5	44.8	Productive tillers per plant, filled grains per panicle, grain yield per plant and 1000 grain weight
IR-79156A x IR-13419	22.6	4.589**	-1.89	1.899**	51.2	59.2	Productive tillers per plant, filled grains per panicle, grain yield per plant and 1000 grain weight, filled grains per panicle and grain yield per plant
IR-79156A x DRR-714-1-2-R	19.6	2.542**	-1.89	0.978*	31.3	38.3	Panicle weight, flag leaf length, spikelet fertility, filled grains per panicle, grain yield per plant, 1000 grain weight and grain yield per plant
IR-68897A x R-48	21.1	4.957**	0.72**	-0.874	41.2	48.7	Panicle weight, flag leaf length, productive tillers per plant, filled grains per panicle, 1000 grain weight and grain yield per plant
IR-68897A x R-51	21.6	3.777**	0.72**	0.866	44.9	52.6	Flag leaf length, productive tillers per plant, filled grains per panicle, 1000 grain weight and grain yield per plant
IR-68897A x R-52	19.8	4.880**	0.72**	-2.122**	32.3	39.3	Plant height, productive tillers per plant, 1000 grain weight and grain yield per plant

HETEROSIS

Commercial exploitation of heterosis in rice today is a profitable proposition. It is obviously important that the crosses are compared with released hybrids rather than merely comparing with their mid / better parent. So, in the present study the performance of the experimental crosses were compared with that of the most popular released medium duration hybrid DRRH-2 and variety JGL-1798 in order to estimate the magnitude of standard heterosis so that the crosses with high heterotic potential could be isolated for further evaluation and commercial cultivation. Wide range of both positive and negative significant standard heterosis was observed in both seasons for all the traits studied. Similar findings were reported by earlier workers Deoraj et al. (2007), Eradasappa et al. (2007) and Rosamma and Vijayakumar (2007) (days to 50% flowering, plant height, productive tillers, panicle length and filled grain per panicle), Panwar et al. (2002) (spikelet fertility), Mishra and Pandey (1998) and Aditya et al. (2012) (flag leaf length), Tiwari et al. (2011) and Aditya et al. (2012) for most of yield and yield

contributing characters. Promising cross with standard heterosis (over checks, DRRH-2 and JGL 1798) for yield contributing traits in rice during *Kharif* and *rabi* are presented in Table 6. Early maturing hybrids are desirable as they produce more yields per day and fit in multiple cropping systems. Twenty three hybrids recorded significant negative heterosis over JGL-1798. During *kharif*, top ten hybrids viz., DRR-14A x R-42, DRR-14A x IR-10198, IR-80555A x IR-44, IR-80555A x JGL-11118, IR-79156A x IR-42, IR-79156A x R-49, IR-68897A x R-44, IR-68897A x IR-13419, IR-68897A x IR-10198 and IR-68897A x JGL-11118 and during *rabi* IR-80555A x IR-66 were significantly heterotic for earliness, when compared with both the standard checks. Shorter plant type is an important character of a hybrid to withstand lodging. All the hybrids were taller over the check JGL-1798 during *kharif* and shorter over the check DRRH-2 during *rabi*, this showed significant standard positive and negative heterosis, respectively. During *kharif*, twenty seven hybrids over DRRH-2 and during *rabi* twelve hybrids over JGL-1798 registered significant standard negative heterosis.

Table 6: Promising cross with significant standard heterosis (over checks, DRRH-2 and JGL 1798) for yield contributing traits in rice during Kharif and rabi

Season	<i>Kharif</i>			<i>Rabi</i>		
Character	Hybrid	DRRH-2	JGL 1798	Hybrid	DRRH-2	JGL 1798
Days to 50% flowering	DRR-14A x R-42	-14.25**	-8.92**	DRR-14A x R-42	-8.66**	-
	DRR-14A x IR-10198	-12.47**	-7.03**	DRR-14A x R-49	-8.42**	-
	IR-80555A x R-44	-12.47**	-7.03**	DRR-14A x R-51	-8.42**	-
	IR-80555A x JGL-11118	-13.74**	-8.38**	DRR-14A x IR-10198	-8.42**	-
	IR-79156A x R-42	-11.96**	-6.49**	DRR-14A x DRR-714	-8.168**	-
	IR-79156A x R-49	-12.47**	-7.03**	DRR-14A x JGL-11118	-8.17**	-
	IR-68897 x R-44	-14.76**	-9.46**	IR-80555A x IR-66	-26.98**	-
	IR-68897 x IR-13419	-12.47**	-7.03**			
	IR-68897 x IR-10198	-12.74**	-7.3**			
	IR-68897 x JGL-11118	-12.47**	-7.03**			
Plant Height	DRR-14A x R-49	-7.8**	18.84**	DRR-14A x R-43	-25.00**	-10.68**
	DRR-14A x IR-64	-6.34**	20.72**	DRR-14A x R-44	-18.97**	-3.49**
	DRR-14A x JGL-11118	-10.07**	15.91**	DRR-14A x R-47	-25.01**	-10.8**
	IR-80555A x R-42	-9.87**	16.17**	DRR-14A x R-48	-22.94**	-8.21**
	IR-80555A x R-46	-7.02**	19.84	DRR-14A x IR-64	-25.42**	-11.17**
	IR-68897A x R-44	-11.79**	13.7**	DRR-14A x IR-13419	-29.56**	-16.11**
	IR-68897A x R-51	-7.98**	18.61**	DRR-14A x DRR-714	-24.68**	-10.29**
	IR-68897A x R-52	-7.55**	19.16**	DRR-14A x JGL-11118	-25.13**	-10.82**
	IR-68897A x IR-13419	-11.11**	14.57**	IR-80555A x R-42	-23.92**	-9.38**
IR-68897A x JGL-11118	-6.84**	20.07**	IR-80555A x R-46	-21.48**	-6.48**	
Panicle length	DRR-14A x R-46	11.18**	11.75**	IR-80555A x IR-10198	-26.37**	-12.32**
	IR-79156A x R-42	10.96**	9.6**	IR-68897A x R-42	-19**	-3.52**
	IR-79156A x R-43	12.1**	10.73**			
	IR-79156A x R-482	9.41**	8.07**			
	IR-79156A x R-49	7.83*	8.27*			
	IR-79156A x R-52	8.98*	7.87*			
	IR-79156A x R-54	12.31**	10.93**			
	IR-79156A x R-56	19.9**	25.54**			

Season	Kharif			Rabi		
Character	Hybrid	DRRH-2	JGL 1798	Hybrid	DRRH-2	JGL 1798
	IR-79156A x IR-66	8.1*	17.26**			
Panicle weight	DRR-14A x R-64	27.94**		DRR-14A x R-42	10.37**	11.84**
	IR-79156A x R-44	17.65**				
	IR-80555A x IR-10198	13.97**				
	IR-79156A x R-49	17.65**				
	IR-79156A x R-51	30.15**				
	IR-79156A x IR-64	27.21**				
	IR-68897A x R-56	27.21**				
	IR-68897A x JGL-11118	26.47**				
Flag leaf width	DRR-14A x IR-10198	12.96**				
	DRR-14A x DRR-714-1-2-R	16.67**				
	IR-80555A x R-56	16.67**				
	IR-79156A x R-48	14.81**				
	IR-79156A x R-51	14.81**				
	IR-79156A x DRR-714-1-2-R	27.78**				
	IR-79156A x JGL-11118	12.96**				
Productive tillers per plant	DRR-14A XR-47	23.76**	25.24**	IR-8055A x R-48	71.42	33.33**
	DRR-14A XR-48	14.59**	15.96**	IR-8055A x IR-13419	74.26	35.92**
	DRR-14A XR-56	13.18**	14.52**	IR-80555A x DRR-714-1-2-R	62.71	26.56**
	IR-80555A X R-42	13.41**	14.76**	IR-79156A x R-42	82.24	41.74**
	IR-80555A X IR-66	20.94**	22.38**			
Number of grains per panicle	DRR-14A x R-43	13.33**	20.37**	DRR-14A x IR-10198	21.16	6.64*
	DRR-14A x R-47	32.89**	41.15**	IR-79156A x IR-13419	25.79	10.71**
	IR-80555A x R-49	25.34**	33.13**	68897A x R-51	23.6	8.78**
	IR-80555A x R-51	25.69*	33.49**	68897A x R-52	20.19	5.78*
	IR-79156A x R-52	10.58*	17.45**			
	IR-79156A x IR-13419	10.96**	17.86**			
	IR-68897A x R-43	10.54**	17.41**			
	IR-68897A x R-42	15.46**	22.63**			
IR-68897A x JR-42	15.3**	22.47**				
Productivity per day	DRR-14A x R-42	60.38**	50.51**	DRR-14A x DRR-714	30.54	46.27**
	DRR-14A x R-47	35.9**	27.54**	IR-8055A x R-42	29.72	45.35**
	DRR-14A x R-52	65.65**	55.46**	IR-8055A x R-48	31.49	47.34**
	DRR-14A x R-54	48.89**	39.72**	IR-8055A x R-56	51.39**	69.63**
	IR-80555A x R-46	38.27**	29.76**	IR-8055A x IR-64	26.15**	41.35**
	IR-80555A x R-47	51.93**	45.58**	IR-8055A x IR-66	24.49**	39.48**
	IR-80555A x R-49	55.71**	46.13**	IR-68897A x R-48	46.67**	64.34**
	IR-80555A x R-51	37.93**	29.44**	IR-68897A x R-51	49.82**	67.87**
	IR-68897A x R-46	47.19**	38.13**	IR-68897A x R-52	52.42**	70.79**
1000 grain weight				DRR-14A x R-49	28.68**	7.79*
				IR-80555A x R-42	27.91**	7.14*
				IR-79156A x R-49	33.59**	11.91**
				IR-79156A x IR-10198	23.46**	11.8**
				68897A x R-46	30.25**	9.11**
				68897A x R-48	27.91**	7.14*
				68897A x R-51	28.16**	7.36*
				68897A x R-52	29.26**	8.28*
Spike let fertility				DRR-14A x DRR-714-1-2-R	30.54**	46.27**
				IR-8055A x R-42	29.72**	45.35**
				IR-8055A x R-48	31.49**	47.34**

Season	<i>Kharif</i>			<i>Rabi</i>		
Character	Hybrid	DRRH-2	JGL 1798	Hybrid	DRRH-2	JGL 1798
				IR-8055A x R-56	51.39**	69.63**
				IR-8055A x IR-64	26.15**	41.35**
				IR-8055A x IR-66	24.49**	39.49**
				IR-68897A x R-51	49.82**	67.87**
				IR-68897A x R-52	52.42**	70.79**

*, ** 5% and 1% level of significance respectively

Longer panicle is generally associated with more number of spikelets and this is one of the attributes for higher grain yields in rice hybrids. During *kharif* DRR-14A x R-46 and nine hybrids involving CMS line IR-79156A with R-42, R-43, R-48, R-49, R-52, R-54, R-56 and IR-66 showed significantly positive standard heterosis over both the checks Panicle weight is positively associated with grain yield. During *kharif*, eight hybrids viz., DRR-14A x R-64, IR-80555A x IR-10198, IR-79156A x R-44, IR-79156A x R-49, IR-79156A x R-51, IR-79156A x IR-64, IR-68897A x R-56 and IR-68897A x JGL-11118 constantly performed well with positively significant heterosis over check DRRH-2 and DRR-14A x R-42 registered positively significant heterosis over the checks during *rabi*. During *kharif*, for flag leaf width seven hybrids viz., DRR-14A x IR-10198, DRR-14A x DRR-714-1-2-R, IR-80555A x R-56, IR-79156A x R-48, IR-79156A x R-51, IR-79156A x DRR-714-1-2-R and IR-79156A x JGL-11118 constantly performed well, as exhibited positive significant standard heterosis over check DRRH-2.

Number of productive tillers per plant is known to directly contribute towards grain yield. During *kharif*, five hybrids viz., DRR-14A x R-47, DRR-14A x R-48, DRR-14A x R-56, IR-80555A x R-42 and IR-80555A x IR-66 and four hybrids during *rabi* viz., IR-80555A x R-48, IR-80555A x IR-13419, IR-80555A x DRR-714-1-2-R and IR-79156A x R-432 were exhibited significant heterosis over check JGL1798. As many as nineteen hybrids were registered positively significant standard heterosis over checks DRRH-2 and JGL-1798 during *rabi*. Low grain yields in rice hybrids are attributed mainly to the high sterility percentage. The extent of spikelet fertility directly influences the ultimate product (grain yield). Most of the hybrids exhibited negative heterosis over seasons for this trait during *kharif*. Eight hybrids viz., DRR-14A x DRR-714-1-2-R, IR-80555A x R-42, IR-80555A x R-48, IR-80555A x R-56, IR-80555A x IR-64, IR-80555A x IR-66, IR-68897A x IR-51 and IR-68897A x R-52 registered positive significant standard heterosis over the checks during *rabi*. The hybrids DRR-14A x R-43, IR-80555A x R-52, IR-79156A x IR-13419, IR-68897A x R-43, IR-68897A x R-47 and IR-68897A x R-52 during *kharif* and DRR-14A x IR-10198, IR-79156A x IR-13419, IR-68897A x R-51 and IR-68897A x R-52 during *rabi* registered positive significant standard heterosis over both checks.

Heterosis for grain yield is mainly because of simultaneous manifestation of heterosis for other yield components. The present investigation revealed a high order of heterosis for grain yield per plant. During *kharif*, twenty one hybrids registered positively significant standard heterosis over checks DRRH-2 and JGL-1798. As many as nine hybrids viz., DRR-14A x R-42, IR-80555A x R-47, IR-79156A x R-42, IR-79156A x R-43, IR-79156A x IR-13419, IR-68897A x R-48, IR-68897A x R-51, IR-68897A x R-52, IR-68897A x IR-10198 were excelled standard heterosis over both the checks and in both seasons. The 1000-grain weight of genotypes serves as an indicator to the end product *i.e.*, grain yield.

For the trait productivity per day nine hybrids viz., DRR-14A x R-42, DRR-14A x R-47, DRR-14A x R-52, DRR-14A x R-54, IR-80555A x R-46, IR-80555A x R-47, IR-80555A x R-49, IR-80555A x R-51 and IR-68897A x R-46 during *kharif*, DRR-14A x DRR-714-1-2-R, IR-80555A x R-42, IR-80555A x R-48, IR-80555A x R-56, IR-80555A x IR-64, IR-80555A x IR-66, IR-68897A x R-48, IR-68897A x R-51 and IR-68897A x R-52 during *rabi* excelled positively significant standard heterosis over both checks.

Grain quality of experimental hybrids

Keeping in mind the importance of grain quality in rice hybrids, for top eleven hybrids during *kharif* and *rabi* (Table 4 & 5) were selected to study the quality parameters viz., hulling per-cent, milling per cent, head rice recovery per cent, kernel length (mm), kernel breadth (mm) and L/B ratio. For grain quality, all the superior hybrids were on par with the checks during *kharif* and *rabi*. During the *kharif*, cross combinations IR-79156A x R-44, IR-68897A x IR-10198 and IR-68897A x JGL-11118 recorded more than 57 per cent of head rice recovery and 3.0 of L/B ratio. Hybrids IR-80555A x IR-66 and IR-79156A x R-43 during *rabi* registered more than 50 per cent of head rice recovery and 3.0 of L/B ratio.

Outcome of the present study, two hybrids viz., IR-80555A x R-51 and IR-79156A x R-44 during *kharif* and three hybrids IR-79156A x R-43, IR-68897A x R-51 and IR-68897A x R-52 during *rabi* have been identified as promising rice hybrids possessing high physical grain quality parameters as compared to checks.

Table 7: Physical grain quality parameters for promising hybrids during *kharif* and *rabi*

Kharif													
Hybrids	DRR-14A x R-42	DRR-14A x R-47	DRR-14A x R-54	IR-80555A x R-48	IR-80555A x R-49	IR-80555A x R-51	IR-79156A x R-44	IR-79156A x R-48	IR-68897A x IR-10198	IR-68897A x DRR-714	IR-68897A x JGL-11118	JGL-1798	DRRH-2
Hulling (%)	71	65.5	77.5	78.3	74.6	66	77.5	77.2	79.6	79.5	73.9	76.2	81
Milling (%)	60.8	51.5	67.2	65.1	62	58	62.7	67.2	66	72.3	66	65.5	71.5
Head rice recovery (mm)	53.3	45.3	57.3	56.1	54.1	52.4	57	58.3	59.3	55.3	59.2	59	59.2
Kernel Length (mm)	6.65	5.99	6.15	5.34	6.03	6.07	6.11	5.63	6.59	5.98	6.37	5.36	6.44
Kernel Breadth (mm)	1.79	1.93	2.13	1.88	2.15	1.94	1.82	2.01	1.83	2.17	2.02	1.55	1.9
L/B ratio	3.72	3.1	2.89	2.84	2.8	3.13	3.36	2.8	3.6	2.75	3.16	3.46	3.38
Rabi													
Hybrids	DRR-14A x R-48	IR-80555A x R-47	IR-80555A x R-54	IR-80555A x R-56	IR-80555A x IR-66	IR-79156A x R-43	IR-79156A x IR-13419	IR-79156A x DRR-714	IR-68897A x R-48	IR-68897A x R-51	IR-68897A x R-52	JGL-1798	DRRH-2
Hulling (%)	72	68.6	77.5	75.1	79.7	72	79	76.9	76.5	69.9	79.2	77.4	80.7
Milling (%)	61.6	59	62	68.8	65.4	59.1	67.2	69.3	64.4	60.6	63.8	65.1	71.3
Head rice recovery (mm)	51.3	48.7	47.3	47.8	52.1	52.4	42.3	46.1	38.1	48	47.9	47.2	53.5
Kernel Length (mm)	5.79	6.29	5.74	5.73	5.9	6.62	6.28	6.15	6.2	6.5	5.98	5.41	6.5
Kernel Breadth (mm)	2.21	2.07	1.99	1.79	1.87	2.12	1.94	2.07	2.09	1.82	1.9	1.57	1.92
L/B ratio	2.62	3.05	2.88	3.2	3.16	3.13	3.24	2.98	2.97	3.57	3.15	3.45	3.38

CONCLUSION

Environment, Crosses, GCA and SCA, and their various interactions with environment were significant suggesting that the hybrids did not have the same relative performances among environments. Results on gene action and combining ability indicated that both general and specific combining ability effects are important but predominance of non-additive genetic variance indicated the presence of heterozygosity in the population. As such this type of genetic variance is non-fixable; hence, heterosis breeding is effective for crop improvement. Line IR-79156A, IR-68897A and tester R-51 during both the seasons and testers R-47, R-48, R-49, R-52, R-56, IR-64 and IR-10198 during *kharif* and R-42, IR-66, R-43, R-46, R-56 and IR-13419 during *rabi* were the promising general combiners for grain yield per plant and other traits. These parents used as testers and lines in the cross combinations could be able to realize medium duration hybrids:- hence, these parents can be used in the future breeding programme. Hybrids viz., IR-80555A x R-51 and IR-79156A x R-44 during *kharif* and IR-79156A x R-43, IR-68897A x R-51 and IR-68897A x R-52 during *rabi* have been identified as promising rice hybrids possessing high physical grain quality parameters as well as *per se* performance, *sca* effects and standard heterosis.

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